

Research article

The influence of ecological conditions on the formation of forest communities in the Selbe-Goliin Ekh Nature Reserve (Mongolia)

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Abstract: A classification of forest vegetation in the “Selbe-Goliin Ekh” Nature Reserve was conducted to identify structural features and ecological differentiation within boreal forest communities. Two associations of the class *Vaccinio-Piceetea* were distinguished: *Carici iljinii-Pinetum sibiricae* (dark-coniferous Siberian pine forests) and *Vaccinio vitis-idaeae-Laricetum sibiricae* (light-coniferous cowberry Siberian larch forests). The coenoflora of the first association comprises 38 species of vascular plants and lichens, while the second exhibits greater diversity with 41 species. Analysis of ecological groups revealed distinct differences between the associations. *Vaccinio vitis-idaeae-Laricetum sibiricae* is formed by light-demanding, drought-tolerant species adapted to nutrient-poor soils. *Carici iljinii-Pinetum sibiricae* is represented by shade-tolerant and moisture-loving plants favouring moderately fertile, moist substrates. Differences in the dominant functional groups reflect community adaptation to gradients of light availability, moisture, and soil nutrient status (trophicity). The obtained results underscore the role of ecological differentiation in maintaining biodiversity and the resilience of boreal ecosystems.

Keywords: Braun-Blanquet method, coenoflora, Mongolia, normalised activity, Protected Area

Introduction

There are currently 107 Protected Areas (PAs) in operation in Mongolia, covering a total area of 31.4 million hectares. According to the current classification

system, these territories can be separated to four categories: strict natural reserves (15 sites covering 13.3 million hectares), national parks (34 sites covering 12.7 million hectares), natural reserves (45 sites covering 5.2 million hectares) and natural monuments

(13 sites covering 104 thousand hectares) (Bayaraa, 2011; Oyungerel, 2010).

The “Selbe-Golyn Ekhi” (Mother of the Selbe River) Natural Reserve is of interest. Established in 2012, it covers an area of 2071.5 hectares. This reserve is classified as a Category IV protected area under the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) guidelines. The reserve’s primary objectives are to protect the groundwater sources that supply drinking water to Mongolia’s capital, Ulaanbaatar, and to conserve unique dark-coniferous and light-coniferous taiga ecosystems. The reserve is in the Khentei Highlands, a region that has long been the focus of scientific research.

A significant body of data on the flora and vegetation of the highlands has been accumulated to date.

The first data on the forest vegetation of the southwestern part of the highlands were obtained, and its classification was carried out according to dominant species and edaphic-climatic conditions (Whipper, 1953). The predominant types of plant communities in the Khentei-Chikoi Highlands and their dependence on ecological factors were determined (Korotkov, 1973). Phytogeographic elements of the northern zone of coniferous forests in southern Khentei were analysed, with particular attention paid to the influence of climatic and orographic conditions (Hilbig & Knapp, 1983). Siberian larch (*Larix sibirica*) forests of Western Khentei were studied, and their structure and dynamics in mountain ecosystems were examined (Savina et al., 1988). The flora of Western Khentei forests was investigated, revealing species diversity and ecological relationships (Mühlenberg et al., 2000). The forest vegetation of the Eroo River basin (Southern Khentei) was studied, and the boundaries of altitudinal zones of light-coniferous and dark-coniferous taiga were established. The obtained results made it possible to identify patterns in the distribution of tree species depending on absolute elevation and slope aspect (Dulmasuren et al., 2004). Data on the composition and structure of forest communities in the Malkhan Range and the Chikoi River basin (Northern Khentei) were systematised (Boikov, 2010). The flora of steppes and forest-steppes in the Kherlen River basin (Eastern Khentei) was studied in detail (Safronova et al., 2018). Studies were conducted on larch forests in the northern part of the Khentei-Chikoi Highlands (Malykh & Pak, 2019).

However, there have not yet been any comprehensive studies on floristic diversity and the dynamics of plant communities within the boundaries of the “Selbe-Golyn Ekhi” Reserve. Consequently, it is essential to conduct a thorough study of floristic diversity and analyses changes in plant communities using various indicators.

The findings obtained will help assess the effectiveness of conservation measures and develop strategies for preserving these unique ecosystems.

The study objective is to identify structural characteristics and patterns of ecological differentiation in taiga communities within the “Selbe Goliyin Ekh” Nature Reserve, using the normalised activity index.

Material and methods

Study area

The study was conducted in the upper reaches of the Selbe-Gol River, flowing through the Khentii Upland within the territory of the Selbe Golyn Ekh Nature Park (Fig. 1). The river originates at an elevation of 1850 metres above sea level and, descending to 1350 metres, traverses the southern part of the upland, including the territory of Ulaanbaatar. Its length is 26.2 km, and its drainage basin area is 220 km².

The area features rugged, mountainous terrain consisting of elongated ridges and depressions. Absolute elevations range from 1479 to 2007 metres above sea level, increasing gradually from southwest to northeast.

The climate is characterised by the following parameters: the mean annual precipitation is 600 mm and the snow cover depth are 60–70 cm. The sum of active temperatures during the growing season ranges from 1180 to 1220 °C. The mean temperature in January ranges from -20 to -23 °C, while the mean temperature in July ranges from +15 to +17 °C. The mean annual air temperature is -1.6 °C.

Depending on the geomorphological conditions, cryogenic and Al-Fe-humus soils form under vegetation, forming the basis of the soil cover (Krasnoshchekov, 2013, 2021). Additionally, perennially and seasonally frozen rocks are widespread under taiga forests in this altitudinal belt (Gravis, 1974).

According to botanical and geographical zoning, the study area belongs to the Khentean Mountain

Fig. 1. Map of the study area: Mongolia. The research site is located in the upper Selbe-Gol River. Sample plot locations.

Taiga Province. This province is part of the East Siberian subregion of the Eurasian Coniferous Forest (Boreal) Region.

Data collection and processing

The vegetation was characterised using descriptions made by geobotanical methods (Lavrenko, Korchagin, 1964). These descriptions ($n = 45$) were processed in Turboveg and classified using the TWINSpan method in the IBIS 6.1 software package (Zverev, 2007).

Syntaxonomy was performed using the Brown-Blanquet system (Westhoff & van der Maarel, 1973). The syntaxon nomenclature is in accordance with the requirements of the Code of Phytosociological Nomenclature (Weber et al., 2000). Species abundance was assessed using a five-point occurrence scale (I–V). Taxon names are given in accordance with the works of M. S. Ignatov (1992), S. K. Cherepanov (1995), and M. Andreev et al. (1996).

The floristic composition of the associations was interpreted as a coenoflora in accordance with modern comparative floristic approaches (Kamelin et al., 1987; Bulokhov, 1993). The belt-zonal affiliation of

species was determined using the system developed by L. I. Malyshev and G. A. Peshkova (1984). Life forms (biomorphs) were classified according to the Raunkiaer system (Raunkiaer, 1934) with modern criteria (Pérez-Harguindeguy et al., 2016). The ecological groups were formed using the methods of K.I. Osipov (2005) and L. P. Rysin (2009).

There is no generally accepted methodology for quantitative assessment of a species'/species group's role within a syntaxon. To address N. I. Makunina (2020) proposed using the normalised activity index of species/species groups. This index can be applied to evaluate the role of species/species groups both in the syntaxon as a whole and in its individual functional components (layers, synusia, etc.). The approach is based on the concept of species activity in the landscape (Yurtsev, 2006), with mathematical formalisation developed by L. I. Malyshev (1973).

Normalised activity represents the proportion of a species'/species group's activity relative to the total activity of all species in the syntaxon, expressed as a percentage. Within a syntaxon, this index ranges from 0 to 100%, with the sum of all species' normalised activities equaling 100%. When assessing a species'/species group's role in a specific layer, 100% corresponds to the total activity of species within that layer.

The authors collected the materials for this study during fieldwork as part of a joint integrated biological expedition by the Russian and Mongolian Academies of Sciences.

Results

A comparative syntaxonomic analysis of the forest vegetation in the upper reaches of the Selbe Gol River, located within the Selbe-Golin-Eh Nature Park in Ulaanbaatar, revealed two associations belonging to different alliances and orders within the *Vaccinio-Piceetea* class of taiga vegetation. The structure of the subordinate syntaxa of different ranks is presented below.

Class: *Vaccinio-Piceetea* Br.-Bl. in Br.-Bl., Siss. et Vlieger 1939

Order: *Ledum palustre-Larix gmelinii* Ermakov in Ermakov et Alsynbaev 2004

Alliance: *Pino sibiricae-Laricion sibiricae* Ermakov in Ermakov et Alsynbaev 2004

Association: *Carici iljinii-Pinetum sibiricae* Ermakov 2014

Order: *Lathyro humilis-Laricetalia cajanderi* Ermakov, Cherosov et Gogoleva 2002

Alliance: *Rhododendro daurici-Laricion gmelinii* Ermakov in Krestov et al. 2009

Association: *Vaccinio vitis-idaeae-Laricetum sibiricae* Makunina 2020

The study revealed that the *Carici iljinii-Pinetum sibiricae* association is characterised by 38 species of vascular plants and lichens, while the *Vaccinio vitis-idaeae-Laricetum sibiricae* association includes 41 species.

A comparative analysis of phytocoenoses in light-coniferous and dark-coniferous forests of the “Selbe Goliin Ekh” Nature Reserve demonstrates similar species richness to the mountain taiga forests of the *Vaccinio-Piceetea* class in Siberia, indicating the representativeness of the obtained results.

Normalised activity of mesophanerophytes

The *Vaccinio vitis-idaeae-Laricetum sibiricae* association is represented by mesophanerophytes – Siberian larch (*Larix sibirica*) and Siberian pine (*Pinus*

Fig. 2. Normalised activity of stand species. For the names of syntaxa, see the note to table of [Supplementary material 01](#).

sibirica), characterised by similar normalised activity. In the studied area, lingonberry larches are formed in a continental climate in the mountain taiga belt on well-drained soils. A special feature of these communities is the difference in the ecology of the dominant mesophanerophytes.

Siberian larch is a typical heliophyte and mesoxerophyte, preferring open, illuminated habitats with moderately arid conditions. In contrast, Siberian pine is a semigeliophyte and mesophyte, which allows it to develop successfully in conditions of partial shade and sufficient moisture. Such adaptations contribute to the plantings' resilience to extreme environmental conditions.

The association of *Carici iljinii-Pinetum sibiricae* is dominated by mesophytic and scioheliophytic mesophanerophytes, such as Siberian pine (*Pinus sibirica*) and Siberian spruce (*Picea obovata*). These trees form a canopy and determine the microclimate of the area.

Siberian pine exhibits the highest normalised activity in this ecosystem. It does not inhibit the growth of understory vegetation or the grass-shrub layer; instead, it allows sufficient light penetration, promoting their flourishing development.

Other species in the association, such as Siberian spruce and larch, play a less active role, functioning primarily as companion species. They contribute to ecosystem diversity, while silver birch (*Betula pendula*), which is locally active, acts as a pioneer species, colonising disturbed areas (Fig. 2).

The composition of the stand reflects the dynamics of post-fire or successional stages, where

Fig. 3. Normalised activity of nano- and microphanerophyte species. The names of the syntaxa are given in the note to table of [Supplementary material 01](#).

Fig. 4. Normalised activity of species of the sub-topological tiers: shrubs - microphanerophytes and nanophanerophytes; grasses – hemicryptophytes, hamophytes, geophyte; mosses and lichens. The names of the syntaxa are indicated in the note to table of [Supplementary material 01](#).

Siberian larch and pine compete for light and water, demonstrating their adaptation to droughts, periodic fires, and other natural influences.

The role of nano- and microphanerophytes in the structure of forest communities

Nano- and microphanerophytes occupy an important place in the structure of forest phytocoenoses, accounting for 10 to 30% of the total normalised activity of the species of the sub-topological tiers (Fig. 4). Their species composition varies depending on the type of forest.

In cowberry (lingonberry) forests, heliophytes and mesotrophs, such as *Rosa acicularis* and *Spiraea media*, are most active. Notably, these communities lack the continuous canopy of *Rhododendron dauricum* and *Lonicera altaica*, which is characteristic of cowberry larch forests.

The oligotrophic hamephyte, *Ledum palustre*, dominates in mossy taiga communities, especially in swampy areas, reflecting its association with poor acidic soils. Semioheliophytic hygromesophytes (*Lonicera altaica*, *Ribes nigrum*), adapted to conditions of insufficient illumination and high humidity, predominate in dark coniferous forests (Fig. 3).

All nano- and microphanerophytes belong to mesotrophs, preferring soils with moderate mineral content. Their ecological plasticity contributes to significant species diversity, driven by adaptation to various environmental conditions.

Light-loving and drought-tolerant species (*Betula rotundifolia*, *Rosa acicularis*, *Spiraea media*) form the shrub layer in the *Vaccinio vitis-idaeae-Laricetum sibiricae* association. Shade-tolerant and moisture-loving shrubs (*Lonicera altaica*, *Pentaphylloides fruticosa*, *Ribes nigrum*, *Spiraea dahurica*) predominate in the phytocoenoses of the *Carici iljinii-Pinetum sibiricae* association, confined to more humid and shaded habitats.

This distribution of species reflects their ecological preferences and plays a key role in maintaining the biodiversity of forest ecosystems.

Normalised activity of hemicryptophytes, hamephytes, and geophytes

The grass and shrub layer in the studied forest communities plays a significant role, accounting for 50–70% of the total normalised activity of the species of the sub-topological layers (Fig. 4).

The normalised activity of plant species of the grass and shrub layer is especially high in *Vaccinio vitis-idaeae-Laricetum sibiricae*, where this indicator reaches 71.8%, while in dark coniferous cedar forests (*Carici iljinii-Pinetum sibiricae*) the normalised activity of species decreases to 51.8%.

The composition and activity of species in the grass-shrub layer varies significantly depending on their typological affiliation.

Hemicryptophytes, geophytes, and hamophytes dominate light coniferous forests. The most active plants include long-rooted geophyte *Carex amgunensis* F. Schmidt and hemicryptophyte *Lathyrus humilis* (Ser.) Spreng. as well as hemicryptophytes *Vicia venosa* (Link) Maxim and *Maianthemum bifolium* (L.) F.W. Schmidt.

Xeromesophytic species (*Carex argunensis*, *Vicia villosa*) demonstrate increased resistance to periodic desiccation, which allows them to successfully exist in conditions of variable moisture.

Fig. 5. Normalised activity of species of the grass and shrub layer (100% is the total normalised activity of species of the sub-topological layers). An explanation of the abbreviated names of the zone-zone groups is given in the note to table of [Supplementary material 01](#).

The dominant role in dark conifer forests is played by a group of dark conifer plants (Fig. 5). These plants are represented mainly by hygrophytic and sciophytic species such as *Ledum palustre* L., *Linnaea borealis* L. and *Orthilia secunda* (L.). The dark conifer group of plants exhibit high ecological plasticity and can tolerate shading conditions, allowing them to dominate the lower layers of cedar plant communities.

The plant life forms found in the taiga ecosystems of Mongolia are like those in Siberia, as confirmed by research (Besolina et al., 1991; Pyhalova et al., 2007).

The analysis identifies the main ecological groups of plants that make up the structure of two types of taiga communities: *Vaccinio vitis-idaeae-Laricetum sibiricae* and *Carici-iljinii-Pinetum sibiricae*.

Normalised activity of lichens and mosses

The moss-lichen layer (Fig. 4) in taiga forests covers 15–20% of the normalised activity. This layer reflects habitat heterogeneity, which is evident in the differentiation and combination of moss and lichen species with broad ecological amplitudes.

Mesohygrophilous green mosses (*Hylocomium splendens* (Hedw.) Schimp., *Pleurozium schreberi* (Brid.) Mitt.) have a high normalised activity in the *Carici iljinii-Pinetum sibiricae* association.

Under stable moisture conditions, green mosses form dense turfs that contribute to organic matter accumulation and regulate the water regime of the forest floor (Prelovskaya and Kazanovsky, 2022).

The xerotolerant green moss *Rhytidium rugosum* (Hedw.) Kindb., adapted to periodic desiccation and increased insolation (Dugarova et al., 2022), is most active in the larches of the *Vaccinio vitis-idaeae-Laricetum sibiricae* association.

The epigeic, mesophilic lichen (*Peltigera aphthosa* (L.) Willd.) has no specific ecological preference and can be found in both dry and moist forests (Kharpukhaeva, 2010; Enkhtuyaa, 2007).

The widespread moss species *Pleurozium schreberi* and *Ptilium crista-castrensis* (Hedw.) De Not., found in both associations, are indicators of moderate moisture (Tsegmed, 2010).

The moss-lichen layer serves as a bioindicator of humidification and light conditions. Moss species, due to specific adaptations (the structure of the thallus, the features of water metabolism), form an environment that determines the succession processes and productivity of taiga phytocoenoses.

Discussion

The ecological interpretation of the indicator of normalised activity of a species requires the use of the status approach developed by B. A. Yurtsev (1966, 1968).

Within the framework of this concept, the activity of a species acts as an integral indicator that reflects the results of ecosystem adaptation and development under specific landscape and climatic conditions.

The activity of a species is shaped by a combination of various factors, including the ecological range of the species, its spatial distribution across different habitats, as well as the overall number and stability of its populations. These factors work together to create the unique characteristics of each species' behaviour and activity. (Yurtsev, 2006).

In fact, activity is a measure of a species' interaction with its environment, including competition with other species and the influence of both biotic and abiotic factors. It serves as a quantitative expression of the species' coenotic status, which is its position in the communication system of the community, or its ecological niche within the established biocoenosis (Nalimova, 2003, 2006; Chepinoga & Rosbach, 2008; Babich & Ushakova, 2012; Konovalova et al., 2014; Savinov & Nikitin, 2017).

Thus, normalised activity is a standardised measure of the ecological significance of a species within an ecosystem.

Coenoflora analysis, using this indicator (for a specific species or group of species), is an effective method for assessing the impact of the environment on the composition and structure of plant communities.

The normalised activity indicator quantifies the contribution of a particular taxon to the total activity all species of syntaxon, expressed as a percentage (Makunina, 2020).

By comparing forest phytocoenoses, it is possible to identify the features of their vertical structure and activity across different layers: the tree layer, shrub layer, herb-dwarf shrub layer, and moss-lichen layer.

Our data on forests in the Selbe-Goliin Ekhi Nature Reserve (Mongolia) and Tuva (Makunina, 2020) show similar patterns. Larch (*Larix sibirica*) and Siberian pine (*Pinus sibirica*) are the dominant tree species in the tree layer, depending on the typological composition and structure of the forest associations.

Vaccinium vitis-idaea larch forests, however, differ in the composition of associated tree species, with distinct ecological preferences and lower normalised activity. In Mongolia, the *Vaccinio vitis-idaeae-Laricetum sibiricae* association is found in more arid and sunny habitats, leading to the presence of Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*). In Tuva, the association includes Siberian spruce (*Picea obovata*), due to shadier and more humid conditions.

More significant differences in syntaxa are observed in the understory layers. While the normalised activity in the herb and dwarf shrub layer of typologically similar forests varies moderately (50–80%), the shrub layer in Selbe-Goliin Ekhi shows significantly higher values (15–20%) compared to the average in Tuva (~10%). In the moss and lichen layer, the normalised activity of moss in Selbe-Goliin Ekhi is like that in Tuvan forests. These differences, especially in the shrub layer, suggest unique ecological conditions or successional processes in the reserve that promote shrub undergrowth development.

Overall, these results are consistent with findings from other studies (Anenkhonov, 2006, 2009; Makunina, 2020).

Conclusion

The classification of forest vegetation within the Selbe-Goliin Ekhi Nature Reserve (Ulaanbaatar) using comparative syntaxonomic analysis revealed two associations: *Carici iljinii-Pinetum sibiricae*

Ermakov 2014, *Vaccinio vitis-idaeae-Laricetum sibiricae* Makunina 2020.

The studied associations exhibit clear ecological differentiation in plant community composition:

- *Vaccinio vitis-idaeae-Laricetum sibiricae* – communities dominated by light-demanding, drought-tolerant plant species adapted to nutrient-poor soils.
- *Carici iljinii-Pinetum sibiricae* – phytocoenoses characterised by shade-tolerant, moisture-loving plants thriving in moderately fertile soils typical of humid habitats.

In the Selbe-Goliin Nature Reserve in Mongolia, the specific environmental conditions and succession processes favour the growth of shrubs in the understory. This is confirmed by comparing indicators of normalised activity with similar forests in the Republic of Tyva, Russia.

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Conflicts of interest

No potential conflict of interest has been reported by the authors, reviewers, or subject editor. No financial interest declared by the authors.

Authors' contributions

(using [CrediT](#))

Yurii Rupyshev: conceptualisation, methodology, project administration, writing—review and editing; Khadbaatar Sandag: formal analysis, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; Sergey Bazha: formal analysis, project administration, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; Elena Danzhalova: conceptualisation, methodology, project administration, writing—review and editing; Yuily Drobyshev: investigation, resources, writing—review and editing; Evgenii Bogdanov: formal analysis, software, writing—review and editing; Igor

Petukhov: investigation, resources, writing—review and editing.

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Supplementary materials

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Document title: Synopsis of forest associations in the upper reaches of the Salbae-Gol River: *Vaccinio vitis-idaeae-Laricetum sibiricae* and *Carici iljinii-Pinetum sibiricae*, with the geographical and ecological-biomorphological characteristics of individual plant and lichen species

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